

Rethinking Journal classification: Rethinking Journal classification in the twenty-first century in the interests of a higher quantum of scientific output and a more globalized scientific output

Sujay Rao Mandavilli

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Abstract

In this paper, we challenge Jeffrey Beall's still dominant in the psyche approach to journal classification and some other ill-conceived approaches to journal classification, and attempt to show why such reductionist views are harmful to the healthy growth of science. While scientific fraud in any form must be horsewhipped and must not be exonerated or absolved at any cost and under any circumstances, journal classification and all other attendant issues and factors impacting and affecting science and healthy scientific progress must be taken in all the seriousness they deserve and merit, and must be assessed holistically and comprehensively. The scholars' and the researchers' point of view must also be taken into account and consideration at all times, and they must be asked to provide a reasonable and an elaborate justification and validation for all their actions including justifications for their publications in less prominent or less prestigious journals. We also propose an alternative approach to journal classification and ranking, but as no one researcher may be able to think through all the factors impacting and affecting the issue comprehensively enough, we invite other interested and concerned scholars, authors, scientists, researchers and educators to contribute more meaningfully to the benefit of the entire process.

Introduction

“Reductionism is a dirty word, and a kind of 'holistier than thou' self-righteousness has become fashionable.” – Richard Dawkins

According to an article published in the esteemed British newspaper the Guardian on the third of February 2024, the quality of scientific research and research publications remains substandard and appalling for the most part, and the situation is apparently going from bad to worse year after year. A large number of research papers and publications of questionable quality often resort to twisting, distorting and faking data, and compromise publication ethics severely. These bogus research papers are often published in journals of questionable quality, and there is an increasingly large number of retractions in peer-reviewed journals each year; as a matter of fact, this exhibits a galloping and a still bolting trend. This growing scandal has negative implications for fields such as medicine where drug development is jeopardized, and promising and better-quality research output being compromised; often, fake cures are peddled as genuine ones, putting patients health in a quandry. The trustworthiness of scientific publications on the whole is increasingly called into question. In the year 2023 alone more than ten thousand scientific papers were retracted, and the situation is only likely to worsen in the years and decades to come. There are many factors to blame for this; for example, in many universities, scientific publications are tied to academic promotions and the retention of jobs. Most “researchers” therefore lack the temperament and aptitude for research (least of all, they may not exhibit any desire or need to do any good to science or society in general), and may be driven purely by monetary considerations.

This unhealthy trend is sometimes said or thought to have originated in China, though it has since spread to other parts of the world including many other parts of Asia and elsewhere. It is generally believed that there are lapses on the part of many individuals including editors, the editorial board, peer-reviewers, of various scientific journals and the researchers and authors themselves. Scientific paper mills abound. In the field of research, a paper mill is a monetarily incentivized business that publishes poor or fake journal papers that appear to be genuine or bona fide research, but as a matter of fact are fraudulent, and contain concocted or falsified data. This is of course the worst kind of offense imaginable. In many cases, plagiarism, ghostwriting, compromised research ethics and compromised research integrity are also involved. The extent and the magnitude of this problem varies from discipline to discipline, and region to region, but the issue appears to be far more severe in fields such as medicine and the neurosciences where more than one out of ten publications fall into the aforesaid category. Precision, exactitude, rigour and transparency are routinely given the go-by in a large number of cases. However, of late, many watchdog groups such as retraction watch have sprung into action and begun to track retractions comprehensively. All these trends and ideals run contrary to our avowed objective to enhance the quality

of science across the world, and in a diverse set of disciplines. We cannot condone them or justify them at any costs or under any circumstances.^{1 2 3 4 5}

Scientific fraud

A scientific misconduct is a more euphemistic way of explaining a scientific fraud; the latter constitutes a grave misconduct of monumental proportions. A scientific misconduct also refers to the violation of the defined and the accepted codes of scholarly conduct and ethical behaviour in the conduct and publication of scientific research. According to a *Lancet* (an old and an ancient peer-reviewed medical journal) review on "Handling of Scientific Misconduct in Scandinavian countries" provides two different definitions, as reproduced in The COPE report of 1999, namely a Danish and a Swedish one. According to the Danish definition, scientific misconduct is an "Intention or gross negligence leading to fabrication of the scientific message or a false credit or emphasis given to a scientist", while according to the Swedish definition, scientific misconduct refers to "an intentional distortion of the research process through the means fabrication of data, text, hypothesis, processes, procedures or methods from another researcher's manuscript form or publication; or distortion of the research process in other ways." Scientific fraud or scientific misrepresentation is highly and extremely damaging not only to the researcher perpetrating the fraud, but also to the scientific community at large, and science in general. According to a survey carried out in the year 2009, about two percent of scientists have admitted to falsifying data (or maliciously tampering with data) at least once; however, the extent of the crime tends to vary widely from context to context, and from situation to situation. There have been famous scientific hoaxes throughout history such as the Piltdown man hoax in palaeontology perpetuated by one Charles Dawson. Another widely reported scientific scandal was one conducted by a German scientist Jan Hendrik Schon; in this case, his claimed breakthroughs with superconductors were proven to be fabricated and falsified by means of fraudulent data. Scientific fraud has also been attributed to some Indian scholars such as Bharat Aggrawal. This this number is admittedly small, it is still an area of grave concern; such nefarious and unhealthy tendencies must be nipped in the bud if India is to emerge as a scientific superpower, and help other countries rise in science in tun. We therefore condemn all forms of fraud viciously whether arising from India or elsewhere.

Beall's List of 'Predatory' journals

The Beall's List of 'Predatory' journals was a prominent and a widely circulated list of "predatory" journals; the list is now mostly and largely considered to be defunct and was removed by other "concerned" and opposed individuals. This list was conceived by the University of Colorado's librarian Jeffrey Beall on his blog "scholarly open access". The term predatory is normally associated with an exploitative attitude in common and general English language parlance, though we consider this equation to be somewhat

¹ Else, Holly; Van Noorden, Richard (2021-03-23). "The fight against fake-paper factories that churn out sham science". *Nature*. 591 (7851): 516–519.

² "The situation has become appalling': fake scientific papers push research credibility to crisis point", *The Guardian*, 3 February 2024

³ Walsh, John E. (1996). *Unraveling Piltdown: The Science Fraud of the Century and Its Solution*. New York: Random House. ISBN 978-0-679-44444-2.

⁴ Sam Kean (2021). *The Icepick Surgeon: Murder, Fraud, Sabotage, Piracy, and Other Dastardly Deeds Perpetrated in the Name of Science*. Little, Brown and Company.

⁵ Jargin SV. *Misconduct in Medical Research and Practice*. Nova Science Publishers, 2020

reductionist and misleading. The list was sometimes used to refer to publishers who did not perform a thorough and adequate peer-review and those publishers who published for a fee. (or publishers who sought “clients” actively) This list became more widely circulated and disseminated by the mid 2010’s, after which it generally declined. It was officially removed in early 2017, though there were subsequent reports that it resurfaced. Other scholars and researchers have set out to build on Beall’s work subsequently; we cannot endorse such endeavours fully or completely, (neither can we endorse Beall’s criteria for inclusion of journals on the list; in some cases, papers with ungrammatical English and journals with non-western editorial boards were also targeted for inclusion, but this appears to be naïve and uninformed of other cultures) hence this rejoinder. Some entry-level scholars who produce good-quality (often non-conformist or contrarian) work cannot naturally publish in high-end journals. “High-end” journals cannot also be said to free from peer-review biases and peer-reviewer prejudices. Many journal go by academic qualification alone. Some “High-end” journals also charge astronomically high publication fees. The implications of terminologies such as “predatory” are also fraught with overtones and are highly misleading and tantamount to false accusations or tarring a broad spectrum of people with the same brush. Most targets and suspects on his list have never been convincingly accused of any wrongdoing. However, as is still the unfortunate trend today, egregious and publicity-seeking approaches garner more interest and attention, (they are even glamorized) and not assiduous, rigorous and painstaking scholarship. Metrics must also be dynamic and not static; low end journals can evolve into high end journals with the passage of time. This is our two cents on the issue. Gates Open research and PLOS also change APC’s or article processing charges. Does that make them predatory automatically and naturally?

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Furthermore, Beall’s categorizations are not granular or fair enough and do not include or take into consideration a wide spectrum of possibilities. These are also natural and bona fide concerns and must be included in any fair evaluation and assessment processes of publishers. Thus, Beall’s reductionism may actually damage science on the whole. (Is this yet another case of “Academic freedom” damaging science?) Among his large list of critics have included Phil Davis, Joseph Esposito, Rick Anderson librarian at the University of Utah, and City University of New York librarians Monica Berger and Jill Cirasella. Thus, on January 15th, 2017 the list was taken off his website, though it has since reportedly resurfaced in some form. There are also several genuine and noteworthy problems in publishing in high-end journals, and these include:

1. High volume of papers received, and this means a low acceptance rate.
2. Bias towards scholars with academic affiliation.
3. Bias towards scholars with higher academic qualifications and Ph.D.’s.
4. Racism and ideology; western researchers may be preferred, and non-western ones discouraged.
5. Peer-reviewer ignorance or peer-reviewer bias may be present.
6. Peer-reviewer non-availability may be a real concern in many journals.
7. Anti-establishment scholars may not be preferred as there is careerism.

⁶ Deprez, Esmé E.; Chen, Caroline (August 29, 2017). "Medical Journals Have a Fake News Problem". Bloomberg. Retrieved August 30, 2017.

⁷ Baker, Monya (May 9, 2016). "Open-access index delists thousands of journals". *Nature*.

⁸ Butler, D. (2013). "Investigating journals: The dark side of publishing". *Nature*. 495 (7442): 433–435.

8. Young scholars and scholars with novel or non-conformist ideas may not be preferred
9. Some well-established, “high-end” and “predatory journals may also charge high publication fees, making the entire debate over-simplified and reductionist.
10. High end publications take time for publishing often a year or more, and some scholars with a potentially high volume of output may opt for rapid publishing.
11. This oversimplified approach may preclude a grounds up and an inductive study of issues i.e. a case by case study; hence, it may be damaging to science as it attempts a hasty over-generalization of issues.
12. Papers or studies can also be meaningfully evaluated post-publication with positive or negative results. Hence, there is no need for a research paper to be impeccable from the outset.

Problems with over-simplified ranking

Thus, the following problems emanate or arise from any reductionist approach to publisher and publication process assessment

1. It is highly misleading to the public who may not be aware of the nuances and the intricacies of the issue.
2. Deters researchers from publishing as they may stand falsely accused of crimes they did not actually commit.
3. May reduce the quantum of scientific and scholarly output; good research may go unpublished, as researchers may fear to make available their ideas.
4. Papers in languages other than English may go unpublished, and even if they are published, may be unrecognized.
5. There is no incentive to journals to improve their practices and adopt best practices; indeed, best practices are not even defined.
6. It is therefore, and for the aforesaid reasons, highly damaging to science as a whole. This in turn impacts societal progress.

In 2007, the Author presented a paper to ICFAI journal of history and culture which was of course a very high end journal in the field. The reviewer assigned was Dr Gregory Possehl who was also a very eminent scholar in the field albeit with highly outdated ideas; he unfortunately however, proved to be highly puerile and infantile in his approach. He did not do a proper review and made unwarranted and uncalled for racist and personal remarks. He also (despite his overall competence and accomplishments as an Archeologist) proved to be ignorant of the basics of Indian culture. When the author rewrote the paper to address his “concerns”, he refused to do the review as he could not proceed any further with his bogus review. The author escalated his concerns to the editorial board of ICFAI who changed the reviewer. The paper was subsequently reviewed by another competent Indian reviewer without any prejudice or malice, and he approved it without any modification. Dr Gregory Possehl did not come out very well in the entire episode, and came out as being naïve and as a guardian of western elitism despite his many good words about ancient India. He also misled “mainstream” Indian researchers comfortably. We could even describe this as pompous naivety. The Author has never seen and mainstream researchers or scholar as biased and prejudiced as this. His “review” was anything but a review. Now that he is dead, if any other scholar

emerges such as this, he must be challenged, exposed, and nipped in the bud. This paper also therefore seeks to bring out the diversity and the breadth of issues involved and educate the average and the common researcher on the issue. In many fields of the social sciences, the system becomes more complex and daunting as many ideologies come into play. We will therefore, witness all kinds of scholarship, some even making dubious connections between the Rapa Nui of Easter Island and the Tamils. Can the distinction between science and pseudo-science get any more blurred? Who should then be held accountable if people like NS Rajaram play mischief? “Mainstream” scholarship should take a fair share of the blame.

The Author’s work is essentially rebellious and recalcitrant by its very nature. It challenges Eurocentrism in various fields of the science and seeks to prove that any “isms”, by their very nature are damaging to science. How can the author then follow a normal and a conventional publication process? Can he send them to Michael Witzel, Asko Paropla, a Marxist historian, a Dravidian nationalist or a Hindutvavaadin for review? How could the Author have followed a conservative publication model with his large volume of publication output (over fifty papers published)? The Author’s approach can be justified for all controversial topics, and for topics on which there a wide variety of rivalling views. We may have to wait for institutional coherentism to materialize, (this was a concept we had espoused in a previous paper) but that may still be a distant pipedream at present. The Author then chose IJISRT which does a basic peer-review, assigns a DOI, does plagiarism check, and indexes papers. The Author explained his mission to the editorial board of IJISRT, and they supported him gladly and very willingly. Some amount of Hobson’s choice was inevitable considering the good nature of the Author’s work. If the Author had followed a conventional approach, his work would have fizzled out with a resultant loss and a detriment to science. Therefore, a large list of parameters must be adopted while evaluating and journal, and these parameters must be dynamic, not static. These must be reassessed periodically, preferably every year. The list of parameters must include at the very least:

1. The institutional and financial backing of journal along with the background of the promoters.
2. The academic backing of the journal – the editorial board and internal and external advisors and peer-reviewers including their experience, expertise and qualifications.
3. The thoroughness and the meticulousness of the review process and the generation of a meaningful and a comprehensive review report.
4. The indexation practices of the journal.
5. The target audience of the journal; journals with a targeted or an intended scholarly audience must be preferred.
6. The citation index of the journal must be taken into account and consideration.
7. The plagiarism check practices and the generation of plagiarism reports must also be an asset for the journal.
8. The generation of DOI’s is also another important factor.

In addition, the scholar or author in question may also be asked to justify why he has published in such and such a journal. If he has published in a less famous or a less prestigious journal, he may have to give a more convincing justification. Journals may also be classified into Class A, Class B, Class C, Class D, Class E, Class F, Class G. The more granular the classification, the merrier. (Journals are sometime classified into

4 Q's or quartiles namely Q1, Q2, Q3, and Q4. Impact factor and cite score classifications are also sometimes used. The Scimago journal and country rank is also sometimes used. Eigenfactor is an another alternative approach, as is source normalized impact per paper or SNIP. Other approaches include the h-5 index, the Top quartile citation count or TQCC and the Publication power approach or PPA. Other than this, there are some country specific rankings available). However, practical considerations must also be borne in mind. The ranking of journals can also of course improve with the passage of time, and journals must also work towards the improvement of their rankings. The entire get up must as a matter of fact, encourage journals to improve their ranking, (rather than to indict them blindly and cheaply) and both quantitative and qualitative metrics can be used for analysis, but preferably quantitative metrics. We also have an important piece of advice to researchers and this sums up the essence of our approach: Be honest, maintain complete transparency, use a fool proof scientific method, furnish a complete bibliography, and of course no fraud, and no faking of data.

Various kinds of scientometrics, bibliometrics can also be put to good random use here. Reviewers must also eschew careerism as far as possible, and maintain the interests of science and society in mind consistently and at all times. As such, a great deal of critical and crucial thought needs to go into journal ranking and journal classification, as such rankings are unfortunately still often politicized, and we look forward to more work and papers from other scholars and researchers in the days and years to come on this vital issue impacting science. People not only from different disciplines and diverse walks of life within the ambit of science, but also people from different parts of the world must participate and contribute. As is now perhaps common knowledge to many, many people arrogantly or naively believe they can resolve a complex and a multilayered issue using deceptively simple and out of the box solutions. Unfortunately, simple solutions fail to comprehend or grapple with all dimensions pertaining to a complex issue. Thus, the multi layered and multifaceted issue is not satisfactorily or adequately resolved. This was one of the principles on which our entire globalization of science movement was founded, particularly for the social sciences.^{9 10}

Conclusion

In this paper, we had reviewed and challenged Jeffrey Beall's dominant approach to journal classification and some other emerging ill-conceived approaches to journal classification, and had attempted to show why such reductionist views are indeed extremely harmful to the healthy growth of science. While scientific fraud in any form must not be tolerated or accepted at any cost, journal classification and all other attendant issues and factors impacting and affecting science must naturally be taken in all the gravity and the seriousness they naturally deserve and merit, and must be assessed holistically and comprehensively at all times. The relevant scholars' and the researchers' point of view must also be taken into account and consideration at all times, and they must be asked to provide a reasonable and an elaborate justification and validation for all their actions including justifications for their publications in less prominent or less prestigious journals. We had also proposed an alternative approach to journal

⁹ Moed, Henk (2010). "Measuring contextual citation impact of scientific journals". *Journal of Informetrics*. Elsevier. 4 (3): 256–277

¹⁰ Altman, Ann M. (2004). *Early Visitors to Easter Island 1864–1877 (translations of the accounts of Eugène Eyraud, Hippolyte Roussel, Pierre Loti and Alphonse Pinart; with an Introduction by Georgia Lee)*. *Los Osos: Easter Island Foundation*.

classification and ranking, but as no one researcher can possibly think through all the factors impacting and bearing upon the issue comprehensively or systematically enough, we invite other interested and concerned scholars, authors, scientists, researchers and educators to contribute more meaningfully to the benefit of the entire process. We lay to rest the issue at this point but we hope we have, along with other concerned and affected researchers and scholars, have launched an important thought process that can impact all facets of science and scientific activity.